

Diversity and Carbon Storage in Fodder Trees of the Lower and Middle Ouémé Valley, Benin: Ecological and Pastoral Sustainability

Alice Yamah Kollie

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, P. R. China

Fangnon Firmin Fangninou

*College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, P. R. China;
Laboratory of Applied Ecology, Faculty of Agronomic Sciences, University of Abomey-Calavi,
01 BP 526 Cotonou, Benin*

Oscar Teka

*Laboratory of Applied Ecology, Faculty of Agronomic Sciences, University of Abomey-Calavi,
01 BP 526 Cotonou, Benin*

André Boya Aboh

*Laboratory of Applied Ecology, Faculty of Agronomic Sciences, University of Abomey-Calavi,
01 BP 526 Cotonou, Benin;
Laboratory of Animal and Fisheries Sciences, National University of Agriculture, BP 43 Kétou, Benin*

Sèton Hanania Sylvanus Honvou

*Laboratory of Applied Ecology, Faculty of Agronomic Sciences, University of Abomey-Calavi,
01 BP 526 Cotonou, Benin;
Laboratory of Animal and Fisheries Sciences, National University of Agriculture, BP 43 Kétou, Benin*

Anne Wambui Mumbi

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai 200092, P. R. China

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Abstract:

This study examines the species composition and carbon stock of fodder trees within the Lower and Middle Ouémé Valley (LMOV), highlighting the key role these species play in pastoral ecosystems and carbon sequestration. A total of 22 species were identified, with Leguminosae dominating at 36%. Noteworthy six species such as *M. inermis*, *L. sericeus*, *P. santalinoides*, *D. oliveri*, *P. erinaceus*, and *A. leiocarpa* exhibited the highest Importance Value Index (IVI), signifying their importance in local pastoral practices. Our research utilized nondestructive allometric equations to estimate both above and belowground biomass, further assessing the effects of soil and climatic variables on carbon stocks. The carbon stock varied significantly with vegetation type, influenced predominantly by the

density and basal area per hectare. Additionally, the study validated the positive correlation between species richness and carbon storage capacity, supporting the role of biodiversity in enhancing ecosystem resilience. Significant findings from regression models indicated that climate variables generally increased carbon stock, whereas certain soil parameters reduced it. This study underscores the necessity of conserving diverse fodder species to support sustainable pastoralism and carbon mitigation efforts in sub-Saharan Africa.

Keywords: *Fodder trees, Allometric equations, carbon stock, Soil and Climate indicators.*

Introduction

The drought of the 1970s caused dramatic ecological and socioeconomic changes in the Sahelian zone, culminating in waves of herd migration to Sub-Saharan African countries (Teka et al., 2007). As a result, Benin hosts transhumant herds on an annual basis, the majority of which originate from neighboring countries such as Burkina Faso, Niger, and Nigeria, and where they coexist with sedentary herds (Houehanou et al., 2008; Teka et al., 2007). Rangelands are mainly located in the northern and central parts of the country, and livestock systems are still traditional and extensive (Sidi Imorou et al., 2016). Since then, the Lower and Middle Ouémé Valley (LMOV) has been a hotspot for both national and transboundary transhumanists, with an average of 84,000 cattle each year from 2007 to 2013 (Alimi et al. 2015). Thus, for numerous sub-Saharan African regions, pastoral resources are being profoundly degraded (Mebirouk-Boudechiche et al., 2015), which outcomes should be addressed.

Pastoral resources consist mostly of natural grazing, fodder trees, and agricultural wastes. Natural grazing is plentiful and provides the majority of the cattle feed during the rainy season due to its lush green carpet. However, food scarcity during the dry season prompts the use of fodder trees (Sarr et al., 2013; Sidi Imorou et al., 2016). Certain tree species are targeted for better milk production, while others are considered for feed purposes (Barshila et al., 2013). For instance, *Azizelia africana*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus* and *Daniellia oliveri* are among the most commonly utilized (Sèwadé et al., 2017). The breeders' method of collecting these fodder trees to make them available for cattle includes heading and pruning. The heading is currently performed on all individual trees, even juveniles. Such a situation no longer assures tree fruiting and jeopardizes the regeneration of targeted species.

Given the growing number of transhumance herds on grasslands in Benin, it arises the

problem of the sustainability of fodder tree exploitation. Other factors resulting from high population growth such as urbanization, agricultural land extension, logging and charring (Ali et al., 2014; Ousmane et al., 2017; Sèwadé et al., 2016), worsen the state of conservation of fodder trees in the host areas of transhumant breeders. Then, if no effort to renew the fodder trees potential, there will be a crucial problem of the viability of the species used in pastoralism. The management and sustainable conservation of fodder trees necessarily require improved knowledge of the current state and the future dynamics of threats and uses of priority tree species for pastoralism.

Fodder trees represent carbon sinks and their rational management contributes to the mitigation of the harmful effects of global warming. Biomass productivity is essential for the definition of conservation and climate policies (Dumont et al., 2013). In recent decades, several studies were undertaken around the world and in Benin to evaluate the biomass and carbon of different tree species, employing allometric equations (Fonton et al., 2009; Gendehou et al., 2012; Goussanou et al., 2016). Diameter, wood density and height are indicated the most important predictors of tree biomass estimation, which is improved with the crown dimension (Forrester et al., 2017; Huff et al., 2017; Panzou et al., 2016). Moreover, biomass are shown to be influenced by soil and climate factors (de Castilho et al., 2006; Nishar et al., 2017). However, carbon storage potential of fodder trees in Benin is limited.

The current study evaluates the carbon stocks of fodder trees in the Lower and Middle Ouémé Valley using nondestructive allometric equations to estimate both above and belowground biomass and assesses the impact of soil and climate factors on their carbon storage potential.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The research was conducted in the rangelands of the Low and Middle Ouémé Valley (BMOV), situated between 6°30' and 7°35'N latitude and 1°97' and 2°45'E longitude (Figure 1). The BMOV, located within agro-pastoral zones 4 and 5 of Benin, encompasses approximately 3813.144 km² and is shared among seven municipalities that accommodate transhumant populations. The climate in the lower valley is sub-equatorial, with an average annual precipitation ranging from 1100 to 1300 mm, while the middle valley exhibits a Sudano-Guinean climate with annual precipitation between 900 and 1100 mm (Adomou, 2005). The Ouémé River is the principal river shaping the basin's physiognomy. Flooding typically occurs from late August to mid-October, although it can start as early as July and extend until early November (Lalèyè et al., 2004). The floodplains and swamp formations, which serve as the ultimate destinations for transhumance herds, occupy between 7% and 15% of the total area of the BMOV municipalities, amounting to approximately 70,000 hectares (PAIAVO, 2013).

Figure 1. Study Area Location

Sampling Design and Measurement

An exploratory phase was conducted on 10 randomly installed plots (50 m × 50 m), in which fodder tree with Dbh ≥ 10 cm were systematically inventoried to determine the variability among individuals. Indeed, the value of the sampling unit's minimum area (s=0.25 ha) was employed (Sarr et al., 2013). Dbh and total height were measured to calculate the coefficient of variation (CV in %), based on structural parameters like Lorey's mean height and basal area. The number of sampling plots (n=137) for the investigation was therefore calculated using Eq.1 (Dagnelie, 1998).

$$n = \frac{U_{1-\alpha/2}^2 \times cv^2}{e^2} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of plots; $U_{1-\alpha/2}^2$ is the value of the normal law for a risk $\alpha = 0.05$; $U_{1-\alpha/2}^2 = (1.96)^2$; $cv = S/\bar{x}$ (Standard deviation divided by mean of series); e is the marginal error set at 0.1.

Plots were installed every km across the study area, with the center coordinates recorded using GPS. In each plot, tree Dbh was measured with a decameter and total height with a clinometer. Species name and number of trees per species were also documented. For trees forked into "w" main stems below 1.3 m, the diameter was calculated as the quadratic sum of the diameters dsi (i=1,..., w) of the major stem (Eq.2):

$$d = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^w ds_i^2} \quad (2)$$

In each of the five quadrats (5m×5m) of each large plot, fodder seedlings were assessed and the height of saplings and poles was measured.

Sixty-seven plots with cattle passage indices (dung, prints, and mutilation) were designated for wood carbon assessment. The biomass sample across these plots included a diverse range of tree diameters. Fodder trees with DBH

≥ 10 cm in each plot were identified and measured. Circumference measurements were taken at the ground, 1.3 m, and every meter up to 5.3 m using a ladder and ribbon π . Diameter at the top of the stem was computed using linear extrapolation based on the last two recorded diameters when the stem height exceeded 5.3 m (Gendehou et al., 2012; Goussanou et al., 2016). Total tree height and stem height were estimated with a SUUNTO clinometer. A stem wood sample from each tree was extracted at 1.3 m with an increment borer to estimate wood-specific density.

Selection of Priority Species for Livestock

Data from field inventories and literature were used to identify plant species preferred or avoided by cattle. The PROTA4U database provided information on species origin, geographical distribution, forms, and uses. For species identification, references such as Flora of Benin (de Souza, 2008) and Trees, Shrubs, and Creepers from West African Arid Regions (Arbonnier, 2000) were used. Unidentified species were collected and taken to the Laboratory of Applied Ecology. Priority fodder trees were selected based on two criteria: (1) a

quality index on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = weakly palatable to 5 = very highly palatable) and (2) an importance value index (IVI, %) calculated following Eq.3 (Mcghee et al., 2016). Priority species for cattle are those with an IVI greater than 10% and a minimum quality or palatability score of 2.

$$IVI = RA + RD + RF \quad (3)$$

Where RA, Relative *abundance*, is the number of individuals of the species divided by total number of individuals (%), RD, *Relative dominance*, is the sum of basal area of the species divided by sum of basal area of all species (%) and RF, *relative frequency*, is the percentage of plots in which a species is represented (%). The IVI is comprised 0 and 300%.

Soil and Climatic Data

19 Climate and 30 soil data were extracted from Worldclim database (Table 1). The data on which extraction is based, come from geographical coordinates of biomass assessment plots (67 plots).

Table 1. Soil and Climate Variables Used in Model

ID	Variable	ID	Variable
Climate variables		Bio5	Maximum temperature of warmest month
Bio1	Annual mean temperature	Bio6	Minimum temperature of coldest month
Bio10	Mean temperature of warmest quarter		Temperature annual range (Bio5–Bio6)
Bio11	Mean temperature of coldest quarter	Bio8	Mean temperature of wettest quarter
Bio12	Annual precipitation	Bio9	Mean temperature of driest quarter
Bio13	Precipitation of wettest month	Cation measure	
Bio14	Precipitation of driest month	cec1-5	Cation exchange capacity_Horizon 1 to 5
Bio15	Precipitation seasonality (CV)	Soil texture	
Bio16	Precipitation of wettest quarter	clay1-5	Clay_Horizon 1 to 5
Bio17	Precipitation of driest quarter	sand1-5	Sand_Horizon 1 to 5
Bio18	Precipitation of warmest quarter	silt11-5	Silt_Horizon 1 to 5
Bio19	Precipitation of coldest quarter	Soil acidity	
Bio2	Mean diurnal range (Mean of monthly (max temp–min temp))	ph1-5	pHx10_Horizon 1 to 5
Bio3	Isothermality (Bio2/Bio7) (* 100)	Carbon	
Bio4	Temperature seasonality (SD *100)	oc1-5	Organic carbon_Horizon 1 to 5

Source: www.worldclim.org

Note: CV: coefficient of variation, SD: standard deviation

Allometric equation and carbon quantification

Wood density

determined as the dry mass of sampled material divided to its volume. Samples were immediately weighed using an electronic scale with 10g sensitivity. The fresh volume of the sample (v_f , in cm^3) is calculated using Eq.4. The core wood sample was oven-dried at 65°C during 48–72h until the dry mass stabilized, yielding basic wood density (ρ_s in $\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$) as given by Eq.5. Mean wood density of six priority tree species in LMOV was compared with previously published data (Table 2).

$$v_f = \pi \times r^2 \times h \quad (4)$$

$$\rho_s = \frac{M_s}{v_f} \quad (5)$$

where r is the radius, h is the depth of the core wood, M_s is the dry mass of wood sample i and v_f is the fresh volume.

Stem volume and biomass estimation of surveyed trees

A truncated cone model was employed to calculate stem volumes (Netshiluvhi & Scholes, 2001). The stem volume of each tree was obtained by summing the volumes of stem (Eq.6) sections, from the base up to the top of the stem (e.g., between 0 and 1.3 m, 1.3 m and 2.3 m, etc.). Stem biomass (B_{stem}) was estimated by multiplying the basic wood density by the total stem volume value (Eq.7).

$$V_{stem} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{H_i}{12\pi} \right) (C_{1i}^2 + C_{2i}^2 + C_{1i} \cdot C_{2i}) \quad (6)$$

$$B_{stem} = V_{stem} \times \rho_s \quad (7)$$

where V_{stem} is the total stem volume, H_i = height of the stem section. C_{1i} and C_{2i} are circumferences of the truncated cone, n is number of the section of the tree stem.

Stem biomass modelling Function

Stem biomass models were developed and tested following previous approach. Linear biomass functions using only Dbh or a combination of Dbh and stem height were examined. Logarithmic transformation was considered to achieve homoscedastic variance. The stem biomass equation was expressed in linear form (Eqs.8-9). The best models are those with the highest adjusted R^2 and the lowest rRMSE values.

$$\ln(B_{stem}) = x_0 + x_1 \ln(\text{Dbh}) + x_2 \ln(H_{stem}) + \sigma^2/2 \quad (8)$$

$$\ln(B_{stem}) = x_0 + x_1 \ln(\text{Dbh}) + \sigma^2/2 \quad (9)$$

where B_{stem} is the stem biomass (kg), Dbh is the diameter at breast height at 1.3 m (in cm) above ground, H_{stem} is the stem height (m), x_1 and x_2 are model parameters, \ln is the neperian logarithm and σ is the residual standard deviation of the linearized models.

Table 2. Mean Wood Density of Major Fodder Tree Species in LMOV

Species	Current study					previous studies $\rho(\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$ or t / m^3)
	n	Wood Density range (t / m^3)	Mean \pm SD	CV	Dbh range (cm)	
<i>A. leiocarpa</i>	37	0.62 - 0.94	0.72 \pm 0.07	0.10	17.51 - 66.85	0.89 ^a

<i>P. eurinaceus</i>	41	0.62 - 0.88	0.79 ± 0.14	0.17	14.96 - 45.68	0.83 ^a ; 0.74 ^b
<i>L. sericeus</i>	35	0.64 - 0.85	0.72 ± 0.06	0.09	10.82 - 41.38	0.75 ^c ; 0.70 ^e
<i>P. santalinoides</i>	36	0.54 - 0.8	0.62 ± 0.06	0.10	13.69 - 54.11	
<i>D. oliveri</i>	37	0.5 - 0.77	0.66 ± 0.07	0.11	13.37 - 77.35	
<i>M. inermis</i>	35	0.60 - 0.74	0.62 ± 0.04	0.06	10.19 - 60.48	0.63 ^a ;

Note: n= Number of wood sample, CV= coefficient of variation, Dbh = Diameter at breast height
Source: ^a (Chabi et al., 2016); ^b (Sallenave, 1955, 1964); ^c (Goussanou et al., 2016), ^d (Zanne et al., 2010); ^e (Kindt et al., 2015)

Quantification of stored carbon in the main aerial fodder

Aboveground biomass (AGB), comprising biomass components besides the stem like branches, twigs, and foliage, is calculated by converting stem biomass ($V \times \rho$) using a biomass expansion factor (BEF). The latter is often obtained by dividing AGB by stem biomass (Eq.10). The present study used the default value BEF= 3.4 recommended by (IPCC, 2003) for tropical forest ecosystems.

$$BEF = \frac{AGB}{B_{stem}} \quad (10)$$

Below-ground biomass (BGB, Eq.11) was estimated using the assumption that root biomass constitutes 28% of the total tree biomass (Teka et al., 2017). The root-to-shoot ratio is determined by the equation $R = 28 / (100-28)$.

$$BGB = \frac{28}{72} AGB \quad (11)$$

The carbon quantity stored by each individual was calculated for ABG and BGB as mean of 47.5-51% of estimated biomass using Eq.12 by Guendehou *et al.* (2012). The carbon quantity of priority fodder trees was calculated and reported per hectare, multiplying the sum of carbon in a plot by sampling unit area ($s = 0.25$ ha). It was then assessed by vegetation types such as fields, fallow, open forests, shrub and tree savannas in tC per ha. The equivalent carbon dioxide (CO₂) is obtained by molecular weights ratio $CO_2 / C = 22 / 7 \approx 3.67$ (Mcghee et al., 2016).

$$CQ = (V_{stem} \times \rho \times BEF) \times (1 + R) \times CF \quad (12)$$

Where, CQ is carbon quantity and CF = carbon fraction (g C/g dry matter)

Statistical Analysis

All data processed using R software. ANOVA employed to assess carbon storage based on zone, vegetation types, topography, and soil type. Mean structural tests (Newman and Keuls Student test) for different levels of the "type of vegetation" factor were performed using the agricolae package. A linear regression model was developed to evaluate the relationship between carbon stock and soil and climate variables. The Box & Cox transformation from the MASS package was applied to stabilize the residual variance of the model (with a logarithmic transformation selected). The step function in R was utilized to identify the soil and climate variables that contribute to the most parsimonious linear model.

Results

Selection of priority species for pastoralism

Within the pastoral region of LMOV, a total of 22 species from 18 genera and 11 families have been identified (Table 3). The Leguminosae family exhibits the highest representation with 8 species, followed by Rubiaceae with 3 species. Additionally, the families Anacardiaceae and Meliaceae each have two species represented, while the remaining families are each represented by one species. Notably, *Mitragyna inermis* emerges as the dominant species with the highest Importance Value Index (IVI) at 139.61%, followed by *Lonchocarpus sericeus* at

48.94% and *Pterocarpus santalinoides* at 30.57%. These key species, along with *Daniellia oliveri*, *Pterocarpus erinaceus*, and *Anogeissus leiocarpa*, are

the primary fodder trees crucial for pastoralism within LMOV.

Table 3. Major Fodder Tree Species (IVI and Quality Index)

Species	Family	Rel. dens.	Rel. freq.	Rel. dom.	IVI (%)	Qual. ind.
<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i>	Leguminosae	2.86	6.63	1.52	11.01	1
<i>Acacia sieberiana</i>	Leguminosae	0.68	3.87	0.47	5.02	1
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Malvaceae	0.54	2.76	12.40	15.70	1
<i>Albizia zygia</i>	Leguminosae	0.27	3.31	0.18	3.76	1
<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	Anacardiaceae	0.14	0.55	0.13	0.82	1
<i>Anogeissus leiocarpa</i>	Combretaceae	5.31	1.10	7.09	13.50	2
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	1.77	7.73	0.83	10.33	1
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Malvaceae	1.50	4.42	4.49	10.41	2
<i>Cola lau Cola laurifolia</i>	Sterculiaceae	0.27	0.55	0.34	1.16	1
<i>Daniellia oliveri</i>	Leguminosae	5.45	11.05	10.65	27.15	2
<i>Dialium guineense</i>	Caesalpiniaceae	0.41	0.55	0.76	1.72	2
<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	Moraceae	0.27	1.10	0.31	1.68	1
<i>Gardenia erubescens</i>	Rubiaceae	0.68	1.66	0.12	2.46	1
<i>Kigelia africana</i>	Bignoniaceae	1.36	3.31	2.72	7.39	2
<i>Lonchocarpus sericeus</i>	Leguminosae	11.72	30.94	6.71	49.37	2
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae	0.54	2.21	0.53	3.28	2
<i>Mitragyna inermis</i>	Rubiaceae	47.82	51.38	35.26	134.46	2
<i>Morinda lucida</i>	Rubiaceae	1.91	2.76	0.62	5.29	1
<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Leguminosae	0.54	3.31	0.92	4.77	1
<i>Pterocarpus erinaceus</i>	Leguminosae	5.99	11.05	5.77	22.81	5
<i>Pterocarpus santalinoides</i>	Leguminosae	9.54	16.57	7.77	33.88	4
<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Verbenaceae	0.41	1.66	0.40	2.47	2

Note: Rel. Dens. = relative density, Rel. Freq. = Relative frequency, Rel. dom. = Relative dominance. Qual. Ind. = Quality index

Stem Biomass Estimation Models

The parameters of the best model are all significant (Table 4). These predict well stem biomass. Dbh and stem height variables positively influence stem biomass. An increase of one unit of Dbh (cm) would result in a 194% increase in biomass. Similarly, increasing one unit of stem height (m) would result in a 68% increase in stems biomass.

Table 4. Parameters of the Global Biomass Model

Parameters	Estimate Value	pval
(Intercept)	-2.50 ± 0.14	0.00
log (Dbh)	1.94 ± 0.04	0.00
log (stem height)	0.68 ± 0.06	0.00

Table 5 presents the estimated parameters and the quality of the fit of the global and specific biomass models. Models with Dbh and height were all significantly better (Table 5B, LR test) compared to models without height (Table 5A). The adjusted coefficients of determination ranged from 82% (*Pterocarpus santalinoides*) to 96% (*Daniellia oliveri*) for models without height and from 93% (*Pterocarpus erinaceus*) to 97% (*Daniellia oliveri*) for models with height. The relative mean squared error is also lower for the models with stem height (17 - 29) than for the models without stem height (25 - 38).

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the global and specific biomass models respectively. There is an inflation of predictions variance for large diameter trees (Dbh > 60cm). *Daniellia oliveri*,

Anogeissus leiocarpa and *Mitragyna inermis* have extreme values of highest diameters (Figure 2).

Carbon Storage of Major Fodder Trees

Overall, the carbon stock varies from 0.21 t/ha to 54.17 t/ha (Figure 7a) for a mean of 9.19 ± 1.27 t/ha. The results of the analysis of variance carried out on the carbon show that the carbon stock varies significantly ($Pr = 0.018$) according to vegetation type (VT), but not significantly following either zone, topography (Topo) or soil type (ST). However, there are large numerical differences between the LOV (3.91 ± 1.00 t/ha) and the MOV (9.91 ± 1.41 t/ha) (Figure 7b). As

soon as one is interested for emissions from land use patterns, mean carbon dioxide (CO₂)/hectare is estimated at 33.72 ± 4.66 t/ha.

In fact, the carbon contribution is greater both in tree savannas (18.23 ± 5.65 t/ha) and in open forests (14.39 ± 4.55 t/ha) compared to the contributions in fields (8.71 ± 1.51 t/ha), shrubby savannas (5.73 ± 2.77 t/ha) and fallow (4.58 ± 0.84 t/ha). The mean multiple comparison test of different vegetation types shows that only tree savannas have a statistically different mean carbon stock compared to other formations.

Table 5. Estimated Parameters and Fit Quality of Global and Specific Biomass Models

Species	Parameters			Fit quality				
	x_0	x_1	x_2	LR test	R ² adj (%)	rRMSE (%)	$\sigma^2/2$	df
(A) Model with Dbh $\ln(B_{stem}) = x_0 + x_1 \ln(Dbh) + \sigma^2/2$								
Global	-1.84 ± 0.16	2.03 ± 0.05			89	34	0.15	225
<i>M. inermis</i>	-1.82 ± 0.29	2.00 ± 0.09			94	31	0.12	34
<i>D. oliveri</i>	-2.62 ± 0.27	2.24 ± 0.08			96	25	0.09	36
<i>L. sericeus</i>	-2.22 ± 0.41	2.18 ± 0.14			88	37	0.14	34
<i>P. erinaceus</i>	-2.72 ± 0.52	2.34 ± 0.16			84	32	0.14	40
<i>A. leiocarpus</i>	-1.44 ± 0.39	1.94 ± 0.12			88	30	0.13	36
<i>P. Santalinoides</i>	-0.97 ± 0.41	1.68 ± 0.13			82	38	0.14	35
(B) Model with Dbh + stem height $\ln(B_{stem}) = x_0 + x_1 \ln(Dbh) + x_2 \ln(H_{stem}) + \sigma^2/2$								
Global	-2.51 ± 0.13	1.93 ± 0.04	0.70 ± 0.05	8.29***	94	26	0.11	224
<i>M. inermis</i>	-2.70 ± 0.33	2.03 ± 0.07	0.53 ± 0.13	0.65***	96	22	0.10	33
<i>D. oliveri</i>	-2.99 ± 0.24	2.12 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.12	0.43***	97	17	0.07	35
<i>L. sericeus</i>	-2.94 ± 0.32	2.11 ± 0.10	0.67 ± 0.12	1.33***	94	29	0.10	33
<i>P. erinaceus</i>	-3.33 ± 0.35	2.16 ± 0.11	0.87 ± 0.12	1.81***	93	23	0.09	39
<i>A. leiocarpus</i>	-1.62 ± 0.25	1.70 ± 0.08	0.71 ± 0.10	1.54***	95	20	0.08	35
<i>P. Santalinoides</i>	-2.34 ± 0.25	1.77 ± 0.07	0.86 ± 0.09	2.13***	95	19	0.07	34

Note: *** $Pr(> |t|) < 0.001$, ** $Pr(> |t|) < 0.01$, * $Pr(> |t|) < 0.05$; x_0 , x_1 and x_2 are the parameters of model, B_{trunc} = stem biomass in Kg, H_{stem} = stem height in meters, df = degree of freedom, σ = standard residual error of the model, rRMSE = Relative mean square error, R² adj = Adjusted coefficient of determination.

Carbon Storage of Major Fodder Trees

Overall, carbon stock ranges from 0.21 t/ha to 54.17 t/ha (Figure 4), with a mean of 9.19 ± 1.27 t/ha. Analysis of variance indicates a significant variation in carbon stock ($p = 0.018$) based on vegetation type, but not significantly influenced by zone, topography, or soil type. However, substantial numerical differences exist between LOV (3.91 ± 1.00 t/ha) and MOV (9.91 ± 1.41 t/ha) (Figure 4a). For land use emissions

estimation, the mean carbon dioxide (CO₂) per hectare is estimated at 33.72 ± 4.66 t/ha.

Three savannas (18.23 ± 5.65 t/ha) and open forests (14.39 ± 4.55 t/ha) contribute significantly more to carbon storage compared to fields (8.71 ± 1.51 t/ha), shrubby savannas (5.73 ± 2.77 t/ha), and fallow (4.58 ± 0.84 t/ha) (Figure 4c). In different vegetation types, only tree savannas exhibit a statistically significant

difference in mean carbon stock compared to other formations.

Figure 2. Biomass Model (kg) of Priority Fodder Tree Species in the LMOV

Figure 3. Biomass Model (kg) for Each of Six Fodder Tree Species

Figure 4. Carbon Stock in Across (a) Valley Zone, (b) Soil Type, (c) Vegetation and (d) Topography

Influence of Soil and Climate Variables on Stored Carbon

The most parsimonious linear model, employing 12 predictors as explanatory variables, demonstrates a good fit (Shapiro-Wilks normality test: $Pr = 0.43$, Breusch-Pagan error homoscedasticity test: $Pr = 0.19$). The results of the linear regression, conducted on the logarithmic scale of carbon stock with respect to soil and climate variables (Table 6). A total of 12 soil and climate variables (Bio15, Bio17, Bio4, cec3, cec4, oc3, oc5, ph2, ph5, sand4, silt2, and silt4) were retained in the most parsimonious model, explaining 30% of the variability in carbon stock.

Climate variables such as Precipitation seasonality (Bio15), Precipitation of the driest

quarter (Bio17), and Temperature seasonality (Bio4) positively influence carbon stock. For instance, a one-unit increase in Precipitation seasonality (Bio15) would result in an average increase of 49% in carbon stock. Conversely, soil variables including Cation exchange capacity Horizon3 (cec3), Organic carbon Horizon5 (oc5), potential Hydrogen Horizon2 (ph2), and Silt Horizon2 (silt2) have a negative impact on carbon stock. Specifically, an increase of one unit in Cation exchange capacity Horizon3 would lead to an average decrease of 86% in carbon stock. These results suggest that specific climate variables positively influence carbon stock, while soil variables have a negative impact on it.

Table 6. Carbon Stock Regression (Logarithmic Scale) on Soil and Climate Variables

Soil and climate factors	Estimate	Std.Error	t-value	Pr (> t)
(Intercept)	-75.40	33.67	-2.24	0.029
Bio15	0.49	0.26	1.85	0.070
Bio17	0.25	0.12	2.04	0.047
Bio 4	0.02	0.01	2.30	0.025
cec3	-0.86	0.33	-2.65	0.010
cec4	0.84	0.33	2.55	0.014
oc3	0.47	0.24	1.96	0.055
oc5	-0.45	0.24	-1.87	0.066
ph2	-0.82	0.28	-2.94	0.005
ph5	0.65	0.19	3.40	0.001
sand4	0.23	0.08	2.92	0.005
silt2	-1.01	0.28	-3.60	0.001
silt4	1.29	0.28	4.55	0.000

Discussion

This study's use of the Importance Value Index (IVI) and Quality Indices to assess the preference of livestock for certain fodder trees aligns with broader conservation goals. By identifying species that are both highly valued by livestock and adaptable to changing environmental conditions, our research supports the development of targeted conservation strategies that can mitigate the impacts of climate change and land degradation on pastoral ecosystems. The prioritization method employed contrast with other involving ethnobotanical and economic survey (Sèwadé et al., 2017). Instead, it was designed to directly observe the species' palatability and availability, allowing for a more flexible assessment that could highlight potentially valuable fodder species based on actual usage and field observations.

Our findings highlight the dominance of Leguminosae, representing 36% of species diversity, echoing similar trends noted in Burkina Faso (Sanou, 2014) and Benin (Sèwadé et al., 2017). Conversely, Combretaceae species have been identified as prevalent within Senegalese agro-pastoral systems (Sarr et al., 2013). Such disparities in species dominance likely reflect the variation in environmental factors such as soil and climate, which exert a

considerable influence on the distribution of vegetation types in sub-Saharan Africa region.

Building on the core findings of species preference and distribution influenced by environmental variables, recent studies also underscore the importance of genetic diversity within these plant families as a determinant of resilience to climatic stressors. Research indicates that genetic variations within the Leguminosae family enhance its adaptability to diverse soil types and climatic conditions, thereby influencing its dominance in various ecosystems (Khatun et al., 2021). This insight complements our understanding of why Leguminosae are prevalent in specific regions and underlines the significance of genetic factors in plant distribution patterns.

The carbon assessment conducted in the grazing landscapes of the Lower and Middle Ouémé Valley (LMOV) underscores the critical role of fodder trees in carbon sequestration, effectively contributing to the mitigation of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions—a principal greenhouse gas and a significant contributor to global warming (Titeux et al., 2017). Variability in carbon stocks is observed across different types of vegetation, predominantly influenced by the density and basal area per hectare. Research suggested that areas with larger-diameter trees generally report higher carbon storage, echoing findings in

diverse ecosystems including savannas, fields, and open forests (Shirima et al., 2015).

Furthermore, the substantial carbon stocks in the LMOV can be attributed not only to physical parameters such as tree size and density but also to the diversity of species within these ecosystems. Study reports a positive correlation between species richness and carbon accumulation, affirming that greater biodiversity enhances the carbon storage potential of these areas (Zanvo, 2016). This relationship underscores the ecological value of maintaining high species diversity, which contributes to ecosystem resilience and functionality

The predominance of Leguminosae species in these fields is particularly significant. Known for their nitrogen-fixing capabilities, these species not only enrich soil fertility but also serve dual purposes by providing fodder and acting as effective carbon sinks. This multifunctionality is crucial for sustainable agricultural practices, as demonstrated in agroforestry systems where such trees exhibit enhanced growth rates and biomass production. However, the impact of local environmental factors such as soil quality and climate conditions on carbon storage capabilities cannot be overlooked. These conditions significantly influence tree volume and biomass, suggesting a complex interplay between biotic and abiotic factors that govern carbon dynamics (Picard et al., 2012).

Conclusion

The findings from this research highlight the critical role of fodder trees in carbon sequestration within the LMOV. By quantifying the carbon storage potential and identifying factors affecting this potential, the study supports the development of targeted conservation strategies. These strategies not only aim to preserve biodiversity but also enhance the ecological resilience of agro-pastoral systems against climate variability. Leguminosae species, in particular, demonstrate significant ecological and practical value, contributing to both soil fertility and carbon storage. The study advocates for the integration of species richness and

environmental management practices in future conservation efforts, ensuring sustainable land use while combating the broader impacts of global warming.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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